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MECHANISMS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UKRAINE

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Abstract: The article presents the results of a factorial PEST study of the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine. The aim of the study is to identify the main features and factors of development of social entrepreneurship in the light of the concept of social responsibility and the use of opportunities and resources of large enterprises to support social entrepreneurship. The systematization of processed information sources shows that in recent years a significant amount of information on the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine has been accumulated. However, the problem of discrepancy between the amount of theoretical knowledge and practical needs to act in the face of constant challenges remains relevant. The methodology of PEST analysis includes desk research, expert surveys, preparation of generalizations, calculations based on survey results, measures regarding the development of social entrepreneurship for the coming years (in the context of factors that experts consider to be the most important). The object of research is theoretical and practical aspects of the development of social entrepreneurship in the context of the concept of social responsibility. The task of the study is to identify the main features and factors of the development of social entrepreneurship in the light of the concept of social responsibility and the use of opportunities and resources of large enterprises to support it. The methodological basis of the study is the basic theoretical and methodological provisions of economic sciences, normative and legal legislation of Ukraine, the works of leading domestic and foreign scientists in the field of economics, marketing and management of social enterprises and social responsibility of business. According to the results of the study, the essence, features and directions of the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine, as well as the insufficient pace and scale of its distribution, are determined. The forms of involvement of large enterprises in promoting the development of social entrepreneurship in the context of social responsibility in Ukraine are substantiated. The results of the study can be used in enterprises, regional communities, regional and state authorities, and non-governmental organizations.

The results of the study are as follows:

- 1) PEST factors for the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine are unstable;
- 2) instability is best expressed in groups of political and socio-cultural factors (the risk of socio-economic and political instability is related to the institutional capacity of civil society organizations and the potential for decentralization);
- 3) the main challenges are grouped by economic factors (e.g., dependence on international donors, insufficient budget funding, low competitiveness);
- 4) there is an imbalance in the group of technological factors (access to online resources has the greatest weight among all the factors proposed for assessment in the PEST analysis format, while the lack of necessary equipment and premises has the least weight);
- 5) there is a strengthening of the organizational capacity of civil society organizations, decentralization of power within the framework of administrative reform and the use of online resources;

6) there are socio-economic and political instability, prevalence of social problems, weak definition of social entrepreneurship, violation of legislation, dependence on international funding sources, lack of strong teams, development strategies, financial and marketing plans, lack of tools for assessing social entrepreneurship;

7) none of the analyzed factors was named by the experts as such that may disappear in the future. The authors associate actions for the further development of social entrepreneurship mainly with the possibilities of decentralization. The obtained results are useful for developing strategies for the development of social entrepreneurship at the regional level and for applying the PEST analysis method in further monitoring studies.

Keywords: socio-economic and political instability, PEST factors, social problems, challenges, opportunities

Introduction

Over the past two decades, social entrepreneurship (SE) in Ukraine continues to attract interest as an innovative approach to solving social problems. New opportunities that can provide a significant boost to the growth of the sector are emerging. Among them are the strengthening of local self-government within the framework of administrative reform and the popularization of the idea of an inclusive economy. However, the external environment is characterized by various uncertainties and risks. A continuous complex of political, economic, sociocultural and technological factors strengthens or weakens social entrepreneurship as a whole system. Therefore, regular analysis of this complex of factors is intended to contribute to the formation of development strategies for the coming years.

Literature review

The topic of formation and development of social entrepreneurship is relatively new for domestic economic science and practice and for entrepreneurship as a whole. In recent years, it has been most actively researched by domestic and foreign scientists. First of all, we can mention the works of D. Bornstein, A. Koretskyi, V. Kudrii, K. Liberti, D. Meira, A. Nichols, A. Svynchuk, J. Schumpeter and others. In the works of these scientists, attention is focused on the factors, nature, priorities and challenges of social entrepreneurship. Corporate social responsibility, which has been practiced longer and more widely and has a strong theoretical and methodological base, is a related topic. There are already works by D. Bayura, O. Grishnova, M. Ignatenko and other well-known scientists. Therefore, it is advisable to determine general factors and elements of implementation for effective management and realization both in theory and in practice.

The mission of social entrepreneurship is especially valuable in the period of financial and economic crisis. This is due to the fact that during this period, social problems become more acute and their solution becomes necessary for a significant part of the population, especially the middle class, represented by small and medium-sized entrepreneurs, company employees, professionals and creative intelligentsia, as well as socially vulnerable groups of the population and individuals with disabilities. Their incomes are significantly reduced as many of their activities are restricted. Therefore, they are forced to look for new forms and to some extent combine their resources and efforts for the implementation of social projects.

Thus, social entrepreneurship contributes to the creation of a favorable business environment, a positive social position, the development and implementation of innovations and social solidarity. Together, they make it possible to overcome crisis situations more calmly, quickly and without destructive consequences and losses. The main idea of social entrepreneurship is to achieve social welfare and create favorable opportunities for this (Gulevska-Chernysh, 2018). On the other hand, social entrepreneurship signals the need for social changes and contributes to social changes in every possible way. Social entrepreneurs seek not only to achieve significant economic returns for their investors and themselves, but also to increase their social capital. They pursue value in the form of positive social changes on a large scale.

Results and discussion

PEST factors related to the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine haven't been the subject of special research. However, to a certain extent, they have been reflected in publications devoted to various aspects of this phenomenon. The most thorough research in recent years was conducted by A. Svynchuk (2016), who classified and characterized the main factors (social, economic, regulatory and organizational) that strengthen the development of social entrepreneurship. High pace of the development of social entrepreneurship is related to economic development of countries and social consciousness of citizens, and the intensification of the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine is mostly related to the regulatory and legal basis of its activity, state policy and ensuring the appropriate level of social responsibility of enterprises. The importance of attracting alternative state funding is also taken into account. In 2017, Public Organization "Youth Center for Social Change "SOCIUM-XXI" with the financial support of the Western NIS Venture Fund conducted a study of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine. The results of the survey (non-representative one using the Google platform) have shown organizational forms of activities, types of social entrepreneurship, the nature of activity and the extent of its spread. The main shortcomings of social entrepreneurship have been identified as financial support, lack of qualified personnel and volunteers, own premises and insufficient support from central and local authorities. Financial support, support from central and local authorities, training of managers of social entrepreneurship, expansion of the production and technical base and raising of social awareness are the main factors of the development. The publication "Ecosystem of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine: Challenges and opportunities" presents the results of an applied political economic analysis conducted by the International Association of Social Entrepreneurship (Ecosystem, 2018). The publication describes the participants of the ecosystem - social enterprises, incubators and accelerators, donors and investors - and concludes that the ecosystem is not fully formed. According to the researchers, the main drawback consists in "the lack of systemic interaction and communication between players" (Ecosystem, 2018). There is no methodology for measuring the social effectiveness of social entrepreneurship. Necessary steps include promoting social entrepreneurship, two-way information sharing and networking. It is emphasized that investments in this area require monitoring of financial and social results, promotion of hybrid completion and interaction with the business community, and higher education institutions are considered as potential incubators.

The Ukrainian Forum of Philanthropists (Kokot, 2020) describes the legal system of support for social entrepreneurs, the available financial and non-financial infrastructure and their key characteristics. Low political visibility, stereotypes and lack of awareness, unstable economic and political conditions, high levels of corruption and bureaucracy, legal violations and uncertain access to credit are among the macro-social factors that hinder the creation of a favorable environment for social entrepreneurship. At the same time, it is recognized that there is a significant potential for development.

In recent years, social entrepreneurship in Ukraine is gaining more and more popularity among the public as an effective mechanism for solving socio-economic problems of local communities. The development of a national strategy for the development of social entrepreneurship, which would coordinate the efforts of all interested parties - entrepreneurs, public organizations, donors and the state – is the key to the success and popularization of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine (Gulevska-Chernysh, 2019). It should also be clearly understood that the profit of social enterprises is primarily directed to business development, public works or solving serious social problems. Such enterprises work and make a profit in compliance with all norms of labor legislation, and therefore are not considered charitable organizations. Social entrepreneurship encompasses areas such as education, the environment, poverty alleviation and human rights.

The main reasons for weak development of social entrepreneurship in the country consist in the lack of state support, lack of funds for development, low awareness of the population and insufficient

understanding of social value and effectiveness of such entrepreneurial activity by state structures and citizens. Fear of risk and uncertainty, lack of qualified personnel, lack of fundraising experience using modern financial instruments, insufficient awareness of the role of social entrepreneurship in society are the main barriers to the development of social enterprises (Doluda *et al.*, 2017). Financial barriers include soft loans, lack of necessary equipment and premises, as well as the possibility of hiring qualified personnel and adequate remuneration. The absence of necessary legislative framework is a formal barrier to the formation of social entrepreneurship.

In 2017, thanks to the efforts of a team of authors, a manual on social entrepreneurship was published (Doluda *et al.*, 2017). The manual contains important information about possible organizational and legal forms of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine, business planning, taxation, financing mechanisms, attraction of non-refundable and returnable investments, accounting and reporting. The authors group factors contributing to the development of social entrepreneurship into economic conditions, legislation, human resources and opportunities, such as the support of international funds and organizations.

For example, A. Svynchuk (2017) presents the prospects for the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine, which arise from factors that cannot always be taken into account, and the development scenarios are diverse. These include: 1) society's reaction to numerous social problems and social vulnerability; 2) the consequences of introducing the status of "social enterprise" in Ukrainian legislation; 3) the results of economic development of Ukraine. Given the lack of relevant information, methods for assessing social effectiveness of social entrepreneurship are also of particular importance.

Scientific articles devoted to the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine are very diverse and reveal the characteristics of social entrepreneurship, its organizational and legal forms, business models, features of creation and experience. Starting with the analysis of social entrepreneurship as a tool for solving social problems, the main attention is paid to clarifying its socio-economic characteristics and regulating the development of social entrepreneurship at regional and local levels in connection with administrative reform.

For example, I. Turskyi (2017) summarizes the experience of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine, its main features and functions in the context of an inclusive economy - one of the global development priorities until 2030. The simplest way to implement social entrepreneurship consists in the use of the cooperative ESOP model (a model of joint enterprise ownership by employees and investors). Researchers claim that the application of the ESOP model at enterprises in Ukraine will allow to overcome social inequality, strengthen the middle class and form social entrepreneurship in the regions of Ukraine. O. Lyakh (2018) focuses attention on institutional support for the development of social entrepreneurship. He emphasizes the importance of the development of social enterprises in Donbas to ensure sustainable socio-economic development of society, reduce social tensions and strengthen social capital. A. Duke (Cooperation, 2019) and B. Kosovych (2020) connect the prospects of social entrepreneurship with the formation of economic model of a social state; A. Duke analyzes social entrepreneurship as an innovative form of business organization; B. Kosovych considers the development of social enterprises in Donbas as a key factor in building a social state. At the same time, innovativeness is seen not in advanced management technologies, but in socially significant approaches to the distribution of benefits and the formation of new social values. The researchers assess whether the principles of cooperation are compatible with the principles of social entrepreneurship development (Duke, Social entrepreneurship, 2019). Cooperation between non-governmental organizations, business and the potential of state policy is recognized as the best form of social entrepreneurship in the modern context. The opinion of B. Kosovych (2020) about the need to transform local social enterprises from various forms of philanthropy into effective forms of management seems valid. The researchers have analyzed the feasibility of changes at the level of legal, economic and ideological factors. In particular, they assume that the predominant use of bank loans under state guarantees is expedient given the limited

potential of state financial support (Gulevska-Chernysh, 2018; Gulevska-Chernysh, 2019), from the point of view of foreign experience, current problems and international support of social entrepreneurship, current state and development prospects. Among current problems, the lack of state support and lack of professionals, the lack of understanding of the concept of social entrepreneurship and the lack of a positive attitude towards it, problems of access to investments have been identified. According to the author, the development of social entrepreneurship is complicated by the high cost of resources and an unstable and unpredictable market environment. Despite certain difficulties in the field of ordering and providing social services in accordance with the Law of Ukraine "On Social Services", these opportunities are considered promising for local self-government bodies. K. Yurchenko (2019) considers current challenges of Ukrainian society - military operations and internally displaced persons - as additional reasons for strengthening social enterprises. V. Ivanyshyn *et al.* (2020) emphasize the need to create a favorable institutional environment for social entrepreneurship in rural areas by creating regional centers for the development of social entrepreneurship. The activities of the centers consist in identifying social enterprises, changing the mentality of the rural population and providing practical support to social entrepreneurship. Contrary to the widespread opinion among scientists that the lack of independent legislation on social entrepreneurship is the problem for the development of social entrepreneurship, V. Nazaruk (2018) believes that certain opportunities in this regard exist and there are resources that are not used by traditional business (unused buildings, owned by the community), the interest of large companies in outsourcing, increase in consumer commitment to social entrepreneurship products, and support from international funds and organizations.

The publications analyzed above indicate that in recent years a significant amount of knowledge about the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine has been accumulated. However, views on the macro-environment affecting its functioning are rather patchy, which makes it difficult to form a strategy for the coming years.

System-structural and system-dynamic approaches are the main methodological approaches. This allows to consider the macro-environment of social entrepreneurship as an integral dynamic system, the components of which interact with each other and stimulate their development:

1. Desk research for the collection, analysis and systematization of secondary information on the main characteristics of PEST factors (political, economic, socio-cultural and technological ones), which affect the state of social entrepreneurship at the current stage, development of a questionnaire for conducting interviews with experts.
2. Expert survey to determine the degree of influence of PEST factors on the development of social entrepreneurship. Analysis of results: a) preparation of summary tables; b) calculation of average inflation coefficients for PEST factors and weighted averages taking into account the expected changes of each factor.
3. Development of the most appropriate measures for the development of social entrepreneurship for the coming years (within the framework of the key factors identified by experts in each PEST group).
4. The results of an expert assessment using the PEST method, which are presented in Table 1. It shows the extent to which each factor contributes to the development of social entrepreneurship and allows to develop a set of possible actions that meet the current opportunities and challenges of the macro environment.

In the group of political factors, expert assessments show that the institutional capacity of civil society organizations is the most important factor. Almost equally important are the possibilities of decentralization of power and the challenges of socio-economic and political instability. Assessing the political factors in the development of social entrepreneurship, experts note that strengthening of the institutional capacity of civil society organizations will have the greatest impact on the spread of social entrepreneurship and will be of key importance in the coming years. The process of decentralization in Ukraine, which involves the provision of basic administrative and social services at the level of local communities, will contribute to the spread of social entrepreneurship. Some

services are provided by social enterprises that have great potential at the local level and this should be highlighted. According to the participants, the process of transferring powers to localities within the framework of administrative reform will gain more importance in the future and will contribute to the development of social entrepreneurship. Researchers point to the need to unite the efforts of civil society organizations and local authorities in order for social entrepreneurship to become one of the mechanisms for reducing the negative impact of social problems on vulnerable population groups.

Table 1. The impact of PEST factors on the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine (according to experts' assessments)

Political factors (P)	Weighted average score	Economic factors (E)	Weighted average score
Strengthening the institutional capacity of civil society organizations (CSOs)	6,4	Dependence on funding from international donors and international technical assistance (grants)	6,3
Decentralization, expansion of powers of local self-government bodies	5,9	Development of budgetary activities (support of project activities of CSOs, social order)	4,6
Socio-economic and political instability	5,8	Low competitiveness (problems of obtaining contracts for certain works and services)	4,5
Insufficient understanding of the concept of "social entrepreneurship" at the level of government, society, CSOs	5,5	Launch of targeted bank lending (Western NIS Enterprise Fund (WNISEF) in cooperation with Oschadbank and Kredobank)	4,2
Legal violations	3,4	Development of the venture philanthropy and social investment market	3,8
Sociocultural factors (S)		Technological factors (T)	
Spread of social problems (socio-demographic crisis, poverty, migration, etc.)	6,7	Use of online resources	6,7
Scaling due to public demand, high potential of human capital and CSOs	5,1	Lack of strong teams, development strategies, financial and marketing plans	5,1
Lack of qualified personnel	5,0	Lack of tools for financial and social impact assessment	5,0
Fragile ecosystem, low level of self-organization by merging into specialized organizations	4,9	Formation of incubation / acceleration programs	5,0
Lack of effective interaction mechanisms in the "state – civil society – business" triangle	4,8	Lack of necessary equipment, premises	3,4

Source: developed by the authors based on the results of an expert survey

Socio-economic and political instability in Ukraine, which encourages the creation of social enterprises as a way to overcome these challenges, is another important political factor stimulating the development of social entrepreneurship. Experts believe that the misunderstanding of the concept of social entrepreneurship at the state and societal level is an important factor, and this factor is unlikely to change in the near future.

The lack of legislative regulation of social entrepreneurship is the least important among political factors, and this assessment of experts is supported by V. Nazaruk (2018), who believes that the lack of special legislation does not hold back the development of social entrepreneurship, but on the contrary, allows it to transform from a commercial project of a public organization in a public enterprise, which coincides with the position of V. Nazaruk. Experts do not expect the adoption of a separate law that would directly regulate the functioning of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine in the near future.

The dependence on funds from international donors and international technical assistance (grants) is the most important economic factor that stimulates the development of social entrepreneurship. Experts believe that this dependence will grow in the near future, and therefore emphasize the importance of improving budgetary support. At the same time, some are skeptical about increasing the role of state authorities and local governments in the development of social entrepreneurship, especially through projects and social orders. In this context, social entrepreneurship experts point out that the state has no obligations to social entrepreneurship and does not want to allocate part of the income tax to the development of civil society. In general, social entrepreneurs emphasize that they do not receive support (including financial) from central and local authorities (Final report, 2017). According to experts, low competitiveness and availability of targeted bank financing have almost the same weight (4.5 and 4.2, respectively). In the group of economic factors, entrepreneurial philanthropy and the social investment market have the least weight. A number of researchers point to the need to attract state funding as an alternative to social entrepreneurship. Among them there are the creation of clusters, the issuance of social bonds (Svynchuk, 2016), the introduction of a cooperative model (the model of joint ownership of enterprises by employees and investors) (Turskyi, 2017), the introduction of hybrid financing (Duke, Cooperation, 2019) and the use of preferential bank financing under state guarantees (Kosovych, 2020). The group of sociocultural factors is characterized by the smallest difference in the weight of individual factors. Experts consider the spread of social problems to be the most important factor and predict that the influence of this factor will grow in the coming years. In other words, the increase in the number of social enterprises can be a kind of reaction to the growth of socio-economic tensions. The possibility of such a scenario was studied by researchers in 2017 (Svynchuk *et al.*, 2017) and they found that this factor not only causes a crisis in the health care system, but also affects social protection, for example, the growth of unemployment, the increase in the level of poverty and the fall in the incomes of the working population, Covid-19. It should be noted that this is especially relevant in the context of a pandemic. According to some estimates, the crisis may increase the risk of poverty among traditionally vulnerable population groups (single parents with children, households with children under 3 years old, single pensioners aged 65 and older) and continue the growth of deprivation poverty (Doluda *et al.*, 2017). The unemployment rate (according to the ILO methodology) in the 1st quarter of 2021 compared to the 1st quarter of 2020 increased from 8.6% to 10.5% (situation on the labor market and activities of the State Employment Service in January-July 2021).

In expert evaluations, the potential for scaling and the lack of qualified personnel for social entrepreneurship have the same weight (5.1 and 5.0, respectively). The consensus regarding the organizational aspects of the development of social entrepreneurship also attracts attention. Such socio-cultural factors as instability of ecosystems, low level of self-organization and lack of effective mechanisms of interaction in the "state – civil society – business" triangle have a rather high weight and almost the same assessment (4.9 and 4.8, respectively). The group of sociocultural factors has the smallest difference between the weights of individual factors (6.7 is the highest indicator and 4.8 is the lowest one). Some studies show positive prospects for the development of ecosystems that provide access to knowledge, mentorship, and resources, as well as the transformation of some benefactors into entrepreneurial philanthropists and social investors (Gulevska-Chernysh, 2018; Gulevska-Chernysh, 2019). Great potential is manifested in high social demand for social entrepreneurship, potential reserves of human capital, successful experience and the need for quality social services (Kokot, 2020).

The use of online resources is recognized as an important technological factor in the development of social entrepreneurship. According to experts, its importance will only grow in the coming years. Today, the development of social entrepreneurship is significantly affected by the lack of strong teams, development strategies, financial and marketing plans, tools for assessing financial and social performance. According to experts, these factors will not change in the near future. The lack of tools for assessing financial and social impact (5.0) is compensated by the potential for development of incubation and acceleration programs (5.0). The factor of lack of necessary equipment and material

and technical base has the least weight in the group of technical factors. Thus, the issues of business education, finance and human resource management in the field of social entrepreneurship, which are discussed in academic circles, remain problematic (Yurchenko, 2019).

The results of the expert assessment allow to recommend further actions for the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine (Table 2).

Table 2. The strategy of actions for the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine

PEST factors	Weighted average score	Actions
Political factors (P)		
1. Strengthening of institutional capacity	6,4	Introduce minimum quality standards (principles of transparency, good governance, quality management, cooperation, solidarity, etc.)
2. Decentralization, expansion of powers of local self-government bodies	5,9	The activities of state bodies at the national, regional and local levels within the framework of decentralization should include information provision of social entrepreneurship
3. Socio-economic and political instability	5,8	Accumulate various sources of funding for scaling social entrepreneurship and acquiring the status of social service providers. Initiate the inclusion of such mechanisms in the plans for social and economic development of communities
Economic factors (E)		
1. Dependence on funding by international donors and international technical assistance (grants)	6,3	Use business planning opportunities for financial independence
2. Development of budget activity (support of project activity of public organizations, social order)	4,6	Participate in social procurement, public-private partnership, competitions of social projects, social programs, public procurement, etc.
3. Low competitiveness (problems of receiving contracts for certain works and services)	4,5	Build relationships with power, communities, business representatives
Sociocultural factors (S)		
1. Spread of social problems (socio-demographic crisis, poverty, migration, etc.)	6,7	Involve vulnerable groups in social entrepreneurship, direct and adapt its resources to solve current social issues
2. Scaling by public request, high potential of human capital	5,1	Carry out advertising in information resources, make applied social research at the regional level
3. Lack of skilled personnel	5,0	Include "Social Entrepreneurship" courses in university training programs, to use online and other forms of study
Technological factors (T)		
1. Use of online resources	6,7	Practice learning and external communication through online platforms. Develop an online transition strategies
2. Lack of strong teams, development strategies, financial and marketing plans	5,1	Include teamwork, strategic and financial planning in all forms of training
3. Lack of assessment of financial and social influence	5,0	Test existing assessment methods and develop new ones taking into account the possibilities of further benchmarking

Source: developed by the authors on the results of expert survey

Conclusions

In recent years, companies have drawn their attention to outsourcing. This means refusing to maintain many auxiliary services and departments on their balance sheet. Therefore, they usually order services such as cleaning, transport, courier delivery, office equipment and networks, advertising and public

relations, organization of activities, training services, accounting and production of various components that allow SMEs to develop. Social responsibility that provides assistance to local communities in solving their most relevant problems is another concept of business development. In this case, if a large company concludes a contract for the purchase of services of a social enterprise, it does not require additional subsidies, as it transfers them to outsourcing and at the same time solves a social problem. The increase in the number of such examples of cooperation in Ukraine confirms the thesis that social entrepreneurship has great potential and plays an increasingly important role in social development. The external environment of the development of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine is characterized by instability. The most pronounced instability is observed in political and socio-cultural factors. Challenges of socio-economic and political instability are related to the potential of civil society organizations and decentralization. Despite the lack of qualified personnel, the spread of social entrepreneurship in Ukraine is a response to the spread of social problems. However, social entrepreneurs are in urgent need of basic entrepreneurial competencies, and most of the challenges are combined into a group of economic factors (dependence on international donors, insufficient budget funding, low competitiveness, etc.). Access to online resources has the greatest weight among all the factors proposed for assessments in the format of a PEST analysis. The lack of necessary equipment and logistical base is at the bottom of the list, and solving these problems is currently quite a difficult task. However, overcoming these difficulties can increase the potential in political and socio-cultural spheres. This is due to the fact that: a) communities have labor, infrastructure and other resources; b) transfer of the provision of basic social services to the municipal level imposes new obligations on municipalities and creates new opportunities for the development of social entrepreneurship; c) actions for the development of social entrepreneurship should be coordinated with key areas of national development. This approach can be demonstrated in the work on further monitoring of social entrepreneurship in united territorial communities of Ukraine. The issues of the information society and the possibilities of using online resources in the conditions of the COVID-19 pandemic also require separate interdisciplinary research.

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Conflict of interest

None.

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МЕХАНІЗМИ РОЗВИТКУ СОЦІАЛЬНОГО ПІДПРИЄМНИЦТВА В УКРАЇНІ

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Анотація. У статті представлено результати факторного PEST-дослідження розвитку соціального підприємництва в Україні. Метою дослідження є виявлення основних особливостей та чинників розвитку соціального підприємництва у світлі концепції соціальної відповідальності та використання можливостей і ресурсів великих підприємств для підтримки соціального підприємництва. Систематизація опрацьованих інформаційних джерел свідчить, що за останні роки накопичено значний обсяг інформації щодо розвитку соціального підприємництва в Україні. Однак проблема невідповідності між обсягом теоретичних знань та практичними потребами діяти в умовах постійних

викликів залишається актуальною. Методологія PEST-аналізу включає кабінетні дослідження, експертні опитування, підготовку узагальнень, розрахунки за результатами опитування, заходи щодо розвитку соціального підприємництва на найближчі роки (в розрізі факторів, які експерти вважають найбільш важливими). Об'єктом дослідження є теоретичні та практичні аспекти розвитку соціального підприємництва в контексті концепції соціальної відповідальності. Завдання дослідження полягає у виявленні основних особливостей та чинників розвитку соціального підприємництва у світлі концепції соціальної відповідальності та використання можливостей і ресурсів великих підприємств для його підтримки. Методологічною основою дослідження є базові теоретико-методологічні положення економічних наук, нормативно-правове законодавство України, праці провідних вітчизняних і зарубіжних вчених у сфері економіки, маркетингу та управління соціальними підприємствами та соціальної відповідальності бізнесу. За результатами дослідження визначено сутність, особливості та напрями розвитку соціального підприємництва в Україні, а також недостатні темпи та масштаби його поширення. Обґрунтовано форми залучення великих підприємств до сприяння розвитку соціального підприємництва в контексті соціальної відповідальності в Україні. Результати дослідження можуть бути використані на підприємствах, у регіональних громадах, регіональних та державних органах влади, неурядових організаціях.

Результати дослідження являють собою таке:

- 1) PEST-фактори розвитку соціального підприємництва в Україні є нестабільними;
- 2) нестабільність найкраще виражена в групах політичних та соціокультурних факторів (ризик соціально-економічної та політичної нестабільності пов'язаний з інституційною спроможністю організацій громадянського суспільства та потенціалом децентралізації);
- 3) основні виклики згруповані за економічними факторами (наприклад, залежність від міжнародних донорів, недостатнє бюджетне фінансування, низька конкурентоспроможність);
- 4) існує дисбаланс у групі технологічних факторів (доступ до онлайн-ресурсів має найбільшу вагу серед усіх факторів, запропонованих для оцінки у форматі PEST-аналізу, тоді як відсутність необхідного обладнання та приміщень має найменшу вагу);
- 5) наявні посилення організаційної спроможності організацій громадянського суспільства, децентралізація влади в рамках адміністративної реформи та використання онлайн-ресурсів;
- 6) існують соціально-економічна та політична нестабільність, поширеність соціальних проблем, слабе визначення соціального підприємництва, порушення законодавства, залежність від міжнародних джерел фінансування, відсутність сильних команд, стратегій розвитку, фінансових та маркетингових планів, відсутність інструментів оцінки соціального підприємництва;
- 7) жоден з проаналізованих факторів не був названий експертами як такий, що може зникнути в майбутньому. Дії для подальшого розвитку соціального підприємництва автори пов'язують переважно з можливостями децентралізації. Отримані результати є корисними для розробки стратегій розвитку соціального підприємництва на регіональному рівні та для застосування методу PEST-аналізу в подальших моніторингових дослідженнях.

Ключові слова: соціально-економічна та політична нестабільність, PEST-фактори, соціальні проблеми, виклики, можливості